

macOS from the Terminal - Your System Security at a Glance

Rocco Gagliardi

Defense Department, scip AG
roga@scip.ch
https://www.scip.ch

Marc Ruef (Editor)

Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
https://www.scip.ch

Abstract: Having the security of an macOS at a glance is possible. Whenever you open a new terminal you might see the latest technical details in the welcome screen. This makes it possible to display changes in startup sequences, firewall settings and scan reports very quickly.

Keywords: AD, Apple, Bash, Block, Firewall, GitHub, Mac, Policy, Report, Tool

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2018 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180712> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Apple computers are beautiful (:= very, very well engineered) devices, hardware and software. I still prefer my 15" retina, trackpad, and keyboard to the 30" Dell on my desktop. A reason because I feel comfortable with macOS is because in addition to the shiny graphical Apps, there is a BSD::MachOS in the background. And even if Apple built a lot of software around it, is still ~~some~~ there. For me, configure an interface with *plumb* is a tiny moment of joy.

Sometime, however, I ask myself what is going on on my Mac. Specifically, I want (quick) answers to the following questions:

- Something new in my startup sequence?
- Something like a rootkit somewhere on my system?
- When I'm connected to public network, I'm still reasonably secure?
- What are the outgoing connections on my system?
- How can I use a specific command without reading man or *ddgo* [1] Internet?

There are different possibilities, but since I fire frequently new terminals, I prefer to have the results as welcome screen. So I copied/pasted/modified/wrote some pieces of code and putted in my `.bash_profile`. Refer to *my github repository* [2] for the code.

3. Terminal welcome message

The small checks to execute at Bash start – or ad-hoc, using alias – are:

- *Gatekeeper* [3] status check
- *Kernel Extension* [4] to check how many extensions are installed
- Number of *Applications* [5] allowed/blocked by ALF
- Changes in *startup sequence* [6] during the last 10 days
- Count of entries in `/etc/hosts` to *block connections* [7] to blacklisted hosts
- Number of Listeners
- Number of *pf* [8] rules (pass/block/log)
- Results of *rkhunter* [9] and *Lynis* [10] scans (report is generated once a day, just results are grepped)

Refer to the scripts comments for an explanation of the control.

This give me a quick overview of my system status; even if not exhaustive, covers many important settings.

```
macp 13.01  macp 13.01
Good Morning, rcc! It's Thursday, July 5 2018
-----
Settings:
Gatekeeper:
  Status: assessments enabled
  kext - Kernel Extension User Consent: ENABLED (0)
AppFW state: Firewall is enabled. (State = 1)
Logging: Log Option is throttled
Apps: ALF: total number of apps = 12
  Allowed: 9
  Blocked: 2
  pf: rules=55 pass=15 block=48 log=37
/etc/hosts: entries= 62234 [last update: Jun 28 2018] (to update use: malicious_hosts_update)
Listeners: 11 [20180629: code in /usr/sbin/synchases odb rapportid.sh]
D[Start]: Changes in startup during the last 10 days
*** WARNING: 2 new item(s) in /Library/LaunchDaemons

REM:
Use cheat <command> to obtain cheat-sheet for command.
17f1264b ~
rcc@rccmdp: ttys001: >
```

Figure: Welcome Screen with Security Details

4. pf

ALF is a very easy to use firewall and quickly gives an idea of our exposure, but if you want more control over your traffic, you need to use another tool. I used *Little Snitch* [11], then macOS (Lion) introduced *pf* and I looked at tools to configure them, like *IceFloor* [12] and *Murus* [13].

